

MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF STOMATITIS IN URBAN RESIDENTS

Boymurodova Mehriniso Nurmurodovna

Zarmed University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11259953>

Introduction. Specific elements of the lesion of the oral mucosa (LOM), as a rule, are considered by dermatologists as intraoral manifestations of skin diseases. For example, such pathological conditions as gingivitis, marginal periodontitis, leukoplakia can be independent diseases and have a non-allergic origin [1]. According to various authors, more than 50% of patients with complaints of intolerance to dental materials (IDM) do not have any objective symptoms of the disease at all [2].

Thus, it is relevant to study the morphological changes of the LOM by the method of impression cytology in various pathogenetic variants of the negative impact of orthopedic structures on the LOM, which will allow us to assess its morphofunctional changes.

Purpose. To evaluate morphofunctional changes in the LOM in patients with stomatitis.

Material and methods. 97 patients who came to the Dental Center in Bukhara with stomatitis of various weights voluntarily agreed to the examination work.

During the clinical examination, patients with complaints of IDM were divided into 4 groups:

group 1 (n=28) – patients with objective clinical symptoms of IDM: gingivitis, stomatitis and/or cheilitis localized in the area of non-removable prostheses, of which 12 men and 16 women. The median age of patients in this group was 53.4 [36; 69] years;

Group 2 (n=25) – patients with prosthetic stomatitis (PS) and identified candida, of which 8 men and 17 women with a median age of 57.4 [39; 67] years;

Group 3 (n=13) patients with PS, without fungi of the genus Candida, 4 of them men and 9 women, with a median age of 61 [57; 70] years;

Group 4 (n=17) – patients without objective clinical symptoms, but with complaints of NSM. The median age of patients in this group was 55 [46; 65] years, of which 3 were men and 15 were women.

Group 5 (n=14) was a control group without complaints of IDM and without PS, comparable in gender, age, type of structures and number of dental units, who agreed to be examined for hypersensitivity to dental materials before

the planned replacement of orthopedic structures. The group consisted of 3 men and 11 women with a median age of 56.9 [42; 69] years.

The level of hygiene was assessed using the simplified oral hygiene index OHI-S, and the severity of the inflammatory process was assessed using the GI index (teeth of symmetrical localization of the opposite side of the jaw were evaluated).

The assessment of the state of the SOPR was carried out using the method of impression cytology, the material for which was the prints of the surface of the SOPR. To do this, parts of cellulose acetate discs (PCAD) with a diameter of 13 mm and a pore size of 0.45 μm (Sigma, USA) were placed with tweezers on the surface of the alveolar process (AP) in the area of the causal orthopedic structure so that the base was located closer to the orthopedic structure, and the tip on the lower jaw was from the vestibular on the sides to the transitional fold and to the bottom of the oral cavity – from the oral; on the upper jaw – to the transitional fold from the vestibular side and to the palate – from the oral. The disc was gently pressed against the surface of the LOM for 2-5s, after which, using tweezers, it was placed on a slide with cellular material up, fixed with a 96% solution of ethyl alcohol. Next, the cell material was clarified in xylene and stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

Light microscopy of each sample and photo documentation were performed on a Leica DM2500 microscope at magnification $\times 100$, $\times 200$, $\times 400$, 630, $\times 1000$. For morphometric processing of photographs taken for each sample in 10 at different sites, with an increase of $\times 1000$, the total number of cellular elements and the number of elements of individual cell groups were calculated: unchanged, dystrophically altered, necrotized, binucleated epithelial cells, eosinophils, neutrophils, macrophages, lymphocytes, plasmocytes, fibroblasts. During light microscopy of cell samples obtained by the impression method and further morphometric assessment of the cellular composition, the morphofunctional state of epithelial cells was also evaluated, which allowed us to judge the nature of the process.

The calculations of the indicators were carried out in the Statistica 10.0 program. Nonparametric data were processed using the Mann-Whitney U Test (M-U), the Wilcoxon Matched Pairs Test with an indication of the level of reliability of the calculation (p). The differences were taken as reliable at $p < 0.05$.

The results of the study. The cellular composition of the patient samples of the experimental and control groups was similar and represented mainly by epithelial

cells, among which fibroblasts, fibrocytes, and inflammatory cells were found in different numbers. However, morphometric processing of the material revealed quantitative differences in the studied samples.

In the samples of patients in the control group, single fibroblasts, fibrocytes, and inflammatory cells were identified among epithelial cells mainly of the surface layers of the epithelium. In the material obtained by the method of impression cytology in patients of group 1 with the presence of objective clinical symptoms of IDM in the form of gingivitis, stomatitis and/or cheilitis localized in the area of non-removable prostheses, the presence of a significant number of segmented neutrophils, macrophages, lymphocytes among the epitheliocytes of the surface layers of the integumentary epithelium was noted. Cells with vacuolization of cytoplasm and nuclei were identified among epithelial cells, the phenomena of karyotic and cytolysis. Individual epithelial cells were 2-nuclear (amitosis) and with polyploidy phenomena. This type of cytogram was determined by us as inflammatory and allergic.

This type of cytogram was determined by us as inflammatory and allergic. In the samples of the 2nd group of patients with prosthetic stomatitis (PS) (removable prostheses), epithelial cells of the superficial and spiny layers of the integumentary epithelium prevailed, with phenomena in most of them scalloped nuclei, karyolysis, karyopycnosis, karyorexis, cytoplasmic vacuolization, cytolysis phenomena.

Along with this, there were binuclear epithelial cells (amitosis), as well as fibroblasts, fibrocytes. The inflammatory cells present in large numbers were

They are represented by segmented leukocytes, to a lesser extent lymphocytes, rod-shaped neutrophils and macrophages. We regarded this type of cytogram as inflammatory and dystrophic. In the samples obtained from patients of group 3, among the epithelial cells of the surface layers of the integumentary epithelium were present in significant numbers segmented neutrophils, macrophages, lymphocytes, as well as rod-shaped neutrophils, plasmocytes. Along with this, eosinophils were found in some of the samples. Among the epithelial cells, both cells with vacuolization of the cytoplasm and nuclei, and cells with phenomena of karyotic and cytolysis, were determined. Individual epithelial cells were 2-nuclear (amitosis).

We also defined this type of cytogram as inflammatory and allergic.

In the 4th group of patients without objective clinical symptoms, but with complaints of NCM, cell samples were mainly represented by cells of the surface

layers of the integumentary epithelium, among which there were single fibroblasts, fibrocytes, segmented neutrophils, macrophages.

There were signs of cytoplasmic swelling in individual epithelial cells.

The cytogram of this group approached the cytogram of the control group in its cellular composition.

Conclusions.

1. In patients with intolerance to dental materials and prosthetic stomatitis, orthopedic structures in direct contact with the oral mucosa affect its condition with the development of dystrophic and inflammatory changes.

2. Based on the analysis of cellular samples of the oral mucosa, significant differences were revealed in the studied groups of patients and inflammatory dystrophic and inflammatory-allergic types of cytograms were identified.

3. The use of the method of impression cytology in assessing the condition of the oral mucosa can be used to develop new approaches to diagnosis, prediction and justification of the choice of the most informative criteria for assessing individual predisposition to the development of intolerance and allergy to dental prosthetic materials.

References:

1. Investigation of contact allergy to dental metals in 206 patients / U. Raap [et al.] // Contact Dermatitis. – 2009. – Vol. 60, N 6. – P. 339–343.
2. Величко, Л.С. Профилактика и лечение пациентов с непереносимостью металлических протезов гальванической природы / Л.С. Величко, Н.В. Ящиковский // Современ. стоматология. – 2011. – № 1. – С. 69–71.

